

LISTENING DIFFICULTIES IN LEARNING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *To the difficulties associated with the peculiarities of listening as a type of speech activity and the conditions in which this activity is carried out.*

Key words: *Difficulties, modern, linguistic.*

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, and in particular Russian as a foreign language, the term "auditing" refers to the process of perception and understanding of sounding speech, where perception is characterized by the analysis and synthesis of linguistic means (phonemes, morphemes, sentences, text, etc.), and understanding is the result of the analysis and synthesis of the semantic meanings of these linguistic means

It is believed that in the modern world speech activity is distributed as follows: listening - 45% of the time, speaking - 30% of the time, reading - 16%, writing - 9%:

Regardless of the accuracy of this distribution, it is obvious that listening predominates among other types of speech activity. The educational sphere is a special area where the role and share of listening is much higher than in other areas. Especially when learning a foreign language at the elementary level, when students listen to the explanations and comments of teachers often for several hours a day.

Difficulties in listening are mainly associated with some well-known and well-studied features of this type of speech activity. These features include, among other things, the consistent flow of information and the low volume of auditory memory compared to the visual one. The latter especially applies to listening in a foreign language, during which the ability to retain information in memory when perceiving a message by ear is significantly reduced.

Difficulties associated with the linguistic form of the message can be divided into phonetic and lexical. One of the main phonetic difficulties at the initial stage is the lack of clear boundaries between words.

They merge for students into one continuous sentence, which they cannot divide into segments.

The highest manifestation of this difficulty in listening are some songs, where additional stress shifts to create a rhyme, in some cases, missing pauses between words and sentences, turn such an audio text into one continuous stream.

Another phonetic difficulty is the assimilation of consonants at the junction and in the middle of words, as well as phonetic reduction. Words and phrases that are simple and familiar at first glance may be perceived as unfamiliar. Lexical difficulties include the redundancy of unfamiliar vocabulary, which makes it difficult to understand the general meaning of the message. Some authors emphasize that colloquial formulas, clichés and idioms are of particular difficulty in listening.

The meaning of these expressions is most often not determined by the sum of the meanings of the words that they include. So, it may be difficult for foreigners to understand the meaning of the expression "run headlong", even if all the words are individually familiar to them. In order to successfully resolve lexical difficulties, it is necessary, on the one hand, to teach students the most frequent phraseological units, clichés and speech patterns their use. On the other hand, special attention should be paid to the correct selection of lexical material, which must correspond to the level of students.

When teaching the perception of foreign speech by ear, you need to use sound recordings that allow you to repeatedly listen to the material being audited, pause, imitate the intonation of the statement, dissect speech when listening to individual sounds, words, phrases, sentences. It is recommended to use a sound recording with voices different in timbre, loudness, pitch to create conditions for real communication and to avoid getting used to a particular voice (for example, a teacher). A variety of sound effects can be used as clues for understanding in a sound recording: a locomotive whistle, splashing water, birds chirping, an announcement of an airplane flight, etc. These noise effects will be perceived by students as a kind of clues during listening.

When listening, there are difficulties associated with the peculiarities of speech. Coming to another country, a foreign student, as a rule, interprets the verbal and non-verbal behavior of a native speaker from the standpoint of his culture and his own norms of

behavior in certain situations of communication. This often leads to a misunderstanding of the perceived information and disruption of contact. Therefore, a foreign student must have the ability to perceive and understand the oral text from the perspective of intercultural communication. To do this, he needs background knowledge.

Only with this knowledge, he can correctly interpret the verbal and non-verbal behavior of a native speaker. In addition, it should be noted that important information should be spoken more slowly; secondary, illustrating, duplicating - faster. It must be remembered that at a slow pace, attention weakens, semantic synthesis becomes more difficult, therefore it is important to strive for the optimal pace for the listener to present information, which would correspond to the pace of his speaking in his native language.

In this regard, it is recommended to pronounce texts in such a way as to create natural conditions for communication with the help of facilitating factors: visual support, unhurried pace, familiar voice, etc. But in some cases, "repeated listening is necessary, for example, when an audio text is used to teach speaking (retelling) or written speech (exposition). Abundant listening, along with special exercises, allows you to gradually remove the existing difficulties.

LITERATURE:

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